

Extended-Plasma-Electromagnetic Cosmology (EPEMC)

Forging a new cohesive cosmology with catastrophist-uniformitarian-diffusionism¹ that expands the Human timeline to cover earlier developments in a pre-paleolithic age beginning with Lascaux and Bosnia; a simplified scientific analysis of astro-cosmology and solar system cosmogony based upon high energy stellar plasma-electromagnetic² and LMH³ physics.

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ABSTRACT

The current massive paradigm shifts in Science are due to collaborative research and exposure, which increases rapidly with the advent of the World Wide Web. Almost every older paradigm has fallen under scrutiny, and new evidence emerges daily to support the more scientifically sound Plasma-electromagnetic Cosmology. By understanding how catastrophism and diffusionism are affected by massive plasma-electromagnetic events in recent changes to the Solar System Circuit, researchers will be better able to explain OOPArts, gaps in knowledge, and to simplify physics and other scientific studies, as well as close massive gaps in the literature that continue to dog Science, leaving loopholes for unscientific hypotheses, such as Flat Earth, Ancient Alien, and New Earth Creation. Ignoring the evidence harms the scientific community and perpetuates the racist history in archaeology and Egyptology, but it must be evidence examined in the light of laboratory proven physics, rather than mystical mathematics and science fiction fantasies. EPEMC is an attempt to reduction of the 'equation' of all variables while conforming to Occam's Razor. While no questions in Science are 'off-limits' the author does not include pseudoscientific ideas to make the cosmology more appealing to the mainstream. It is, however, a paper and hypothesis for those that see the failings of the current mainstream paradigm and seek better explanations. This whitepaper is a primer and wrapper for the hypothesis and is updated as more papers are written.

Key words: Diffusionism - Catastrophism - Plasma - Electromagnetism - Pre-history

¹ For definitions and explanation of a workable model, see the Index in Appendix A

² The Jeurgens-Scott Electric Star model

³ Liquid Metallic Hydrogen: Robitaille, Crothers, et al...

Introduction

It shall be possible, and indeed more satisfying, to present a cosmology which is unified, and simple; conforming to the simplicity of Occam's Razor, which also satisfactorily covers all of the facts, and does not omit the evidence of any science. This would eliminate the need for superfluous hypotheses⁴, many of which are officially or near officially falsified already; some which were falsified ere they were formulated, except that their postulators failed (in a pre-Internet age) to do sufficient research to discover this fact before they devoted themselves entirely to the paradigm.

In some cases, the establishment of conspiracies or institutional prejudices would seek to defend (mostly via politics and even worse: popularity) such positions and destroy any science which challenged it, whether realistic or simply conjectural in nature. However, in the Age of Information and at the touch of fingertips, amateur and professional scientists of cross-disciplines have been able to compare and contrast, and to delve from archived scans and reference materials to question mainstream assumptions, presumptions (such as supposed 'consensus science'), and positions that are upon much scrutiny found to be fairly untenable by established facts, evidence, mathematical comparison, or laboratory research; in other words: hard science.

The following is a first collaborative White Paper to establish, as best as possible, an alternative position and create a new cosmology, "Extended Ethereal-Plasma-Electromagnetic Universe." It will contain elements of Electric Universe, Plasma cosmology, Ethereal Mechanics, Quantum Electrodynamics, diffusionism, catastrophism, a modern version of Atlanteanism, and discussions of the ancient alien hypothesis explained through these lenses. In the latter case, it may not be considered the "simplest" explanation, as the alien hypothesis, like Black Holes, are technically unfalsifiable by line of reasoning of the unseen, and are more a matter of a form of theology than of science. However, the application of this hypothesis to it may give a more satisfactory result than none at all for noted phenomena, given the total data set. On the other hand, it will not satisfy some more fantastical or religious audiences.⁵

⁴ <http://www.scmp.com/news/world/united-states-canada/article/2140349/centre-milky-way-teeming-black-holes>
<https://phys.org/news/2016-08-physicists-discovery-nature.html>

⁵ <https://search.app.goo.gl/GsW2>

Analysis

(1)

It appears that “in the beginning” refers to three distinct time periods in humanity’s existence. Allowing for normal evolutionary line of thinking, the first “beginning” would be the sudden emergence of modern mankind, anatomically speaking, now established at 200,000 - 240,000 YBP, based on recent archaeological sites. The date being pushed thus far back enables for our hypothesis and opening up of three other arenas of thought:

1. The “Missing Links” - now establishable as per normal, uniformitarian theorem (it is a wonder they did not insist upon it if not for mere spite of diffusionism) as well as truncated periods of catastrophism which match human worldwide testimony.
2. Atlantean Theory - As more missing land masses emerge - Sundaland, Doggerland, Lemuria, Mauritius, Bimini row, and of course Beringia - the increasing likelihood of lost civilizations grows year by year. This will open for speculation the previously untenable dates for Bosnian pyramids, Gunung Padang, and Gobekli Tepe, as well as the supposed ancient cultures of Paracas, Olmecs, Indo-Europeans, and Australian aboriginals.
3. The development, and loss, of early High Civilization, as evidenced in the Great Pyramids, Mexico, Sumer, and Dwarka.

The immediate push back against this beginning must needs give way to the facts of the Bosnian pyramid (c. 36,000 YBP) whose astronomical, geophysical alignments as well as technical design parameters, combine to create a convincing case of early civilization; as well as the sheer mass of biological, artistic, evidence and logical processes of evolution in human history. After all, time must be allowed for development towards the next phase, as well as the establishment of the sites in South Africa which are hitherto dated most suspiciously but are certainly paleolithic in the extreme. Moreover, one hundred thousand years or more of modern biological mankind, instigated by multiple phases of Ice Ages (necessity is the mother of invention) convinces us of the adequacy of this period to allow for natural, uniformitarian human evolution.

It also enables us to consider the length of time of experimentation with entheogenic plants towards expanding human consciousness. Considering it as diffuse trial and error, oral tradition, and a lack of language and writing skills as we would consider necessary to describe plant experimentation, a basis for the foundational currents of shamanism, would later become actual religious activity (in the paleo and neolithic). This smooth transition would be much more satisfactory to all parties concerned, by decompressing the time requirements and allowing for obvious civilizing influences, as well as cataclysmic and climatic barriers (such as Ice Ages, comets, volcanoes, tsunamis, etc...)

(2)

The second beginning appears to refer to the emergence of modern mankind, consciousness wise, about 24,000-36,000 YBP. This follows the normal line of thinking that technology increases exponentially and with time, while allowing that certain catastrophes may have eliminated our connections to these cultures, albeit we remember them in unexpectedly accurate periods. Plato’s passing on of the legend of Atlantis refers *exactly* to the period of the Younger Dryas end event, 10,600 BCE (9000 years before his time); which is matching almost to the century the dating of Gobekli Tepe. We can say that this period was in existence based upon the findings at Gobekli Tepe in which the mere 10-15% of excavations of the upper portions have already yielded results in “enclosure C” dating to the Age of Leo, and indeed a massive central pillar depicts a lion to confirm

its date. It is unambiguous that this time also is confirmed at the Sphinx by both geology and the anatomy of the Sphinx, which was obviously originally a lion facing Leo at this time period.

Yet also at Gobekli Tepe these 'temples' or enclosures are built sequentially, or serially, and then buried purposefully (probably at the close of a zodiacal or other astronomical era), indicating that the deeper the excavations occur, the older the site will get. (Indeed we can expect this around the world, as was seen at the excavation of Troy, which lay under 30 feet of soil).

Furthermore, the excavations at Gunung Padang indicate a concurrent phase of pyramid building with volcanic plinths in Sundaland in the range of 24,000 YBP. This establishes the minimum value of the genesis of civilization as an idea, before it entered into success at Gobekli Tepe. However we cannot isolate how deep into time this "beginning" is beyond to say that there appears to be a concordance of activity in central Europe and west to Greece at most 36,000 YBP and definitely before Gobekli Tepe. Thus 24,000 YBP being a good average and co-linear with Gunung Padang pyramid building phases, it also supports the paleolithic art phase in Northern Europe at around 17,000-32,000 YBP at Lascaux, for example. Meanwhile it does not exceed the realistic period of migration which is, at maximum to Europe around 40,000 YBP. 8,000 years is sufficient time for an indigenous culture to establish itself, as modern humans to attain modern consciousness through the use of psychedelic plants and fungi, as suspected at Lascaux. It is also roughly the period of confirmed oral traditional myth for aboriginals of Australia and India.

The time period from this beginning to the first "ragnarok" appears to be the origin for the concept of a "first time" (Zep Tepi, Egypt) or "dreamtime" (aboriginals of Australia) which was lost upon the arrival and growing dominion of the Desert Belt. This forced some of the first great migrations and also, allegedly, the collapse of mighty "continents." It will be shown through key eyewitness testimony from South American tribes and Sumerian Legends that this event was precipitated by the arrival of the Moon (Janus, Anu or Nibiru) and a particularly savage cosmo-electric catastrophe, the first or second of at least six more (the Chinese say nine), see Table 2. The evidence for this remains primarily upon the moon itself which displays all of the following mainstream-defying features, which satisfy the EPEM framework:

- Lunar face (towards Earth) majority excavated, especially as compared with lunar back.
- Lunar-Earth entrainment
- Moonquakes despite cooling core
- Perpendicular cratering (vast majority) on lunar face (side of electric arc machining)
- Crater chains
- Multidirectional crater chains
- Rim cratering
- Central "bullseye" peaks in craters taller than rims
- Flat, or even convex crater floors (as opposed to conical/concave), despite lack of wind or water erosion
- Few, but obvious impact craters surrounded by multitudinous non impact craters
- Etc...

There are also concurrent Native American and worldwide myths regarding this event, and rocks were provided by the Lakota to NASA prior to the moon missions, which confirmed the Earth's surface bombardment by lunar rocks.

The next cataclysm is assumed to have occurred toward the end of the Tepe/Navori Cori movement (T-shaped plinths) 9000 BCE and the beginning of the movement towards Mesopotamia, which would require 3,000 more years to commence, inexplicably otherwise. If there be a previous cataclysm, then being the collapse of the

“Atlantean” “continents” (Sundaland, Doggerland, Lemuria, Pacifica, Beringia, and Atlantea) due to Sudden Crustal Displacement was caused most likely by the Expanding Earth’s hotspots weakening the bent crust and combined, again, with the influences of passing nearby solar system bodies (particularly one that was large). In particular there is a myth about the hanging of one of the gods by his “heels”, which has been confirmed to be Uranus, known now to unexpectedly roll upon its side. Was this caused by the passage of a “Planet Nine” (X or Nibiru), or the movement of the sun first through the old solar system, causing the first “Clash of the Titans” during which Saturn (Kronos) lost Earth and Mars to Jupiter (Zeus)? It is unfortunately too convoluted in the myths at this time, although further linguistic analysis may yet reveal the age of the myths in their due order.

How or why the Earth had grown so much through the various Ice Ages is also not readily clear, although a general mechanism is proposed as follows: Solar plasma transformer (parallel) circuit > pumps Earth’s poles full of particles at a vulnerability in the magnetosphere (South America having the largest such weakness explains the massive Pacific Rift nearby) > this in turn heats the proto-water (EZ Water) within the core as we see Jupiter and Saturn be heated from the poles > the water expands as does the number of particles more rapidly than they leave or the water vents upwards to the surface. There has also been a proposed mechanism of either tachyons or baryons that enter the Earth and become trapped, usually when a star goes nova, but possibly at a continuous rate anytime the sun has a solar flare, especially ones large enough to push/peel back the magnetosphere. This constant pumping up of the Earth appears to follow, as nature dictates, a steady increase truncated by sudden, staccato expansion moments.

Cataclysm	Date	Evidence Known
Tiamat incursion Sinking of Atlantis	14000 or 12600 YBP	Younger Dryas event, Carolina Bays (final series), Solon’s report to Plato, Gobekli Tepe “enclosure C”, Enuma Elish
The Deluge - mountains?	10000 YBP	End of Tepe mound event, Nevali Cori
“Divine wind”	7000 YBP	Rig Veda?
Great Flood (Storm)	5600 YBP	The Atrahasis and Gilgamesh
Great Comet Venus/Exodus	3600 YBP	Multiple lines, mound-builders/Adena, Egypt, Mexico, Peru, India, Norse, Greek Myths, China, etc...
Mars/Dark Age of Greece	2680 YBP	Biblical era texts and calendar evidence

Table 1 - List of Proposed cataclysms

(3)

The third beginning appears to be the “Word” that is to say, sounds heard, worldwide, during one period of catastrophic upheavals. This word or sound, “yahwey” or “yahoo” (pronounced by the Cherokee as “ywahoo”) was heard worldwide in diverse peoples and repeated in diverse cultures, spawning in some cases, monotheistic traditions (in the Middle East and China), particularly around the “Desert Belt” which experienced circa-equatorial forces due to near collisional interaction with the planet Venus, which was at that time the “Great Comet” Venus. After “Athena” was removed by her “father” Zeus (Jupiter), from which she had emerged (probably passed through, being previously the planet Hera), she became the “evening star” and “morning star”

and was a number of diverse mythological beings (covered later). This event was in a Heroic period that ended the Age of the Gods, and preceded the modern archaic period from the Zhou Dynasty (Middle Kingdom, Adena) forward.

The events, being highly electrical, and the war between the “gods” of the two pantheons (Aesir and Vanir) both quite visible and in the sky, inspired an age of war, philosophy, and obsession with both our “Fall” from Edin (the agricultural paradise that emerged after the First Time) and with Salvation. The first salvation was in the god of knowledge (Thoth, planet Mercury). However he failed to protect us and it became Ares, the god of War (planet Mars) to defend us from Athena-Venus. Some cults sprang up in favor of a redeemer, the thrice perfect Hermes (Mercury). But war reigned around the world, including in China during the Warring States Period. As war and chaos spread, our next salvation came in the form of war development, chiefly technology. The advent of scientific revolution itself cultivated this fire further and we find ourselves still in the grasp of this paradigm to this very day. We are caught between one paradigm of “turn the other cheek” and embrace wisdom, and the technocracy which has ever developed weapons of war first. From the sword, and trident, which had their first shaping in the plasmoids of the sky to the modern Internet, itself electrical, our paradigm surrounding energy has ever been to embrace the tree of knowledge for war, rather than self-cultivation and improvement, which is regarded as fringe.

In between, we find through modern archaeology and comparative astroarcheology and archaic archaeology and biblical studies, ways to fill the missing gaps.

Take for instance the currently unsmooth, and highly untenable official Egyptology hypothesis that the Great Pyramids are tombs and products of the Middle Kingdom, and that the “bent” pyramid and step pyramids are early examples or attempts. However the oldest of the three is somehow the largest, and a tomb. Setting aside the 100% provable facts of machining, engineering, planning, logistics, and economics of the construction of the world’s greatest ancient marvel, it is certainly not a tomb. There is no evidence that survives scrutiny that it was ever a tomb. No treasures or bodies have ever been found in its sealed chambers, and it is clearly a well orchestrated engineering project based upon the numerological evidence alone. Compare this with the extravagant Valley of the Kings, such as Tutankhamun's tomb, and it becomes absurd to postulate pharaohs of the great power to build pyramids yet not supply even signatures to their own tombs. These are, therefore, clearly engineering projects.

Considering also the need to receive a return on investment, even for a reduced workforce provided it was built with molds of proto limestone, as is likely, it was certainly not coincidental and narcissistic, or the result of a cult of death. There aren’t really any cultures that aren’t interested in death (such as in Tibet where they still practice a form of “death meditation”), so it is to be expected that some of the projects were associated with tombs, but not all, and certainly not the largest three or four.

It seems most logical, based upon the ascertained geological evidence of the Sphinx, and the astronomical alignments given on the site, that the entire Giza project extended from the period previous to the Younger Dryas down til the previous cataclysm to modern Egypt. However the number of catastrophes from the Age of the Gods (Clash of the Titans) led to a total destruction of the people that built them. Though, they appear (via the Olmec and Paracans,) to have gone across the seas and built the Pyramid of the Sun and other American marvels as well. This we can see from the curious “handbag” hieroglyphs (and the use of hieroglyphs) on both sides of the Atlantic, as well as the oral traditions of America and Egypt and Iberia.

They also clearly built the smallest pyramid first (it is clearly older looking) and then increased in size to maximize their power (electrical) reception from the Schumann Resonance. The epitome of their culture was

the Great Pyramid, which gave them electrical power from the Earth, as well as served to honor “Osiris” (Orion) **and** mimic the three large “mons” on Mars, which was, at that time a nearby brethren planet to Earth (formerly Tiamat) in a Saturnian or Jovian system (probably Jovian).

After these “gods”⁶, emulated them by entering into a period of feverish megalithic construction.

In places where caves or dolmens had protected mankind from “hail and brimstone” - probably impact ejecta and meteorites (although large hail can be sustained through electromagnetic repulsion), he quickly re-entered into agricultural, technical, and civilizing cultures with extremely strict religious aspersions. In the case of India, for example, upon seeing the “Bull of Heaven” turned into a Cow (Athena’s Horns and beard, aka Loki’s androgynous form), and then rain down ‘heavenly ambrosia’ (mana; hydrocarbons from Venus’ comet tail), Hindus made it completely illegal to consume bovine meat or even to stop a rampaging bull or cow, as this was the Warrior Goddess in animal form! In other cultures the Bull of Heaven was observed to be ‘killed’ and the Age of Heroes began, based upon the “Great Man” (wounded man, squatter man) who occupied the sky. This Gilgamesh was the basis for many religious happenings, and associated with, alternately, God (Odin) or his Son the Warrior (Thor).

The entire story is summarized in at least three sources: the Norse lineages of the gods, the Rig Veda, and the Egyptian texts. Much of the fourth source, the Mayan codices, were burned, and only part of the story remains. The event took thousands of years but indelibly affected the thought patterns of the modern consciousness of mankind. Such that he slowly, reluctantly, lost the balance found after the consciousness awakening during Zep Tepi that led to Atlantis, and has ever since, failed to re-attain. The greatest example of this has to be the burning of the library at Alexandria. The Chinese obsessively related the story of the downfall from innate nature (xing) to Dao (the typhon/midgard serpent comet tail seen which was self-consuming due to Venus’ orbit, and then later associated with the Milky Way itself), to then civilization and eventually, lawlessness. They associated the downfall with a change in consciousness. Indeed even in North America the Lakota and Ojibwe relate the destruction, as with Noah’s time, to do with the uncivilized, wicked ways of the then modern man. This would, logically, imply that mankind had been previously much more civilized. In Sumeria, the god Enlil was enraged at the “noise” of mankind.

Take in particular the Arthurian legend; itself based upon the movements of real peoples, probably the Welsh/Khumry (descendants of Cimmeria?). In America, already celtic peoples had arrived and begun mound building, as a continuation of religious devotion to the gods, and a hearkening back to a more ideal age. They even built massive (indeed the largest in the world) earthworks to depict the gods, and to keep calendrical alignments. But they refused, absolutely refused to use writing, or the wheel which they must have known about, despite obvious mathematical and logistical knowledge. This is quite strange. Then, upon the arrival of the Khumry, the mixed paleo-mongol-celtic (Algonquin) tribes fought with these newcomers and fought against their civilizing ways, such as in Cahokia). The Lakota, raised massive armies to destroy them, and we can find no other evidence as to why save threat of economic, empirical expansion. (This is assuming there was no Helen of Troy type situation).

⁶ Perhaps tall humans, perhaps with skull elongation practices) were gone, cultures around the world, seeing their collapse but not remembering the precise details of their cultures (post diluvian, for there were multiple Flood events caused by repeated passage near to other satellites of our first and second suns, Kronos and Zeus, themselves brown dwarves in a binary formation, soon to be disturbed from their alignment by the arrival of a main sequence star, Apollo

Afterwards, did they take up the civilizing ways, and forts, and technologies? No. Nor did they take over the stone forts of the Vikings and others who came, and were later slaughtered in the Ohio Valley (perhaps for no more reason than living in the land of the Ancients) in the Hopewell and Ft. Ancient periods? They were clearly against it. This need to stop civilization perhaps parallels the Aztec obsession with the End of the World needing to be prevented via bloodshed (Mars demanding of sacrifice). Meanwhile the simple fact of the mound genesis coming from anode blistering at lightning and thunderbolt strikes had long been forgotten. Perhaps even to the original moundbuilders in America, but we'll never know. Certainly it has remained a mystery in Europe where warfare has perhaps erased most of the best evidence and the rest the Church did (to zealously guard, subconsciously against the polytheism of the past and promote only the Redeemer paradigm, then already 3000 years old).

However, there can be no doubt that the need to bury important chiefs and warriors in conical mounds directly reflects the mindset around the world that it took special permission, and great warrior or leader status (and special knowledge) to get into Heaven. Again, referring to the original Arthurian legends in the Age of Heroes, a wizard, Merlin, with his powers over nature is able to predict birth and death via unknown methods. But, as we see elsewhere, his powers are relegated to the ages of dragons, and not for the period of the Redeemer. This echoes the sentiments of mystical cults from the Middle East to Scandanavia, Yucatan, Peru, and Africa. The change in consciousness - the "revelations" must have preceded the last two major destruction events, and been associated, via legend, with the great First Time, and therefore with the use of entheogens and meditation methods to know more of the Spirit World. This was and still remains a primary religious behavior of the Sami people and Dogon, who retain that ancient worldview and remember the astronomical and magical realities from that time. Yet, according to Genesis, the Tree of Knowledge's fruits caused a destruction of the Tree of Life, both within, and of the Yggdrasil, (colinear alignment of celestial spheres). Around the world, Flood myths concluded that the destructions were caused by improper worship, evil animals, and downright evil men; and salvation only came at the mercy of the Lord(s); in particular to devout, pious, and virtuous men that built rafts and ships that saved humanity. So we see that the consciousness paradigm beneath the cultural, linguistic, and scientific dimensions underwent a drastic change after the third beginning, particularly strengthened by the final Ragnarok, that of Mars' betrayal (berserking) when the planet passed too close to Earth on increasingly destabilized elliptical orbits that resulted, ultimately in the end of the Jovian rule, and beginning of the era of the Sun, new Helios (originally Helios had been Saturn).
What is the nature of this consciousness change?

(4)

Modern research into the particular cave art of megalithic, stone age Europe and Aborigines of Australia and South America, have revealed a sudden change in themes from abundant game to monsters and then to fairies, aliens, gods, and the 'wounded man' around the same period of human discovery of language, psychedelics, and tools. This change clearly precipitated our growth in the proteic period, opening our anatomically modern brains to modern consciousness, and placing upon our species a devout respect for the unseeable forces of nature and the "supernatural." However, as these forces later revealed themselves in epic sky battles, thunderbolts (found in every culture), and resulted in the destruction of human and animal populations, and of mountains and continents, and shamanism lost favor in civilized cultures for direct astrological religions. In some cultural cases widespread, detailed myths - the archaic equivalent of "Star Wars" - was propagated as explanations of celestial sphere movements. In one case at least, if not more, it explained the destruction of a planetoid(s) or moon of a gas giant (then a Titan), becoming the Asteroid Belt. However, note that although this is equally superstitious to the shamanistic viewpoint, it differs in level of violence and in informing mankind of the nature of the gods as themselves, mortals (seen in the Vedas), fallible, and

sometimes, the enemies of mankind. Indeed, in Sumer when gods “misbehaved” sacrifices were withheld to coax the planets and planetoids back into their orbits, so as to stave off destruction. We now know that these were pointless gestures, but because mankind had a) no working model for electro-gravity and no understanding of plasma-electricity and b) had become so conscientious as to believe they must emulate the gods, it can be understood in terms of family dynamics (then the obsession of the world: see Confucius and the Zhou). In particular the ways a son sometimes has to correct the behavior of a mother or a decrepit father or grandfather.

One must realize this was all at a time when our planet, and a few other bodies occupied either a distant stable orbit within the plasma sheath of Saturn (purple dawn, or Dream Time, as the Aborigines called it); or after the discharging of Saturn to his “son” Jupiter, and the “recession of Ra” the chaotic orbit around the Olympian gods, who then clashed unhappily with the other demigods (such as Prometheus) or moons of Jupiter and Saturn (and Uranus and Neptune, the Vanir). Indeed the development of modern consciousness was not despite the cataclysms observed, but owed to them, was influenced by them, and evolved - rapidly - as a survival instinct. The more drugs consumed, and philosophy developed, the more mankind was able to technologically advance and he imagined himself less vulnerable to these great forces. As a force was defeated in the Heavens and moved off, mankind quickly moved to erase the previous paradigms of religion with improvements or perceived moral improvements (such as the Redeemer over the god of war), and as was seen at Alexandria, and the various book and temple burnings in that now archaic time, mankind was zealous to guard the new paradigm from the old, and stamp out the old paradigm’s very memory. Such as the druids, who recalled that Merlinesque period of wisdom, and were subsequently destroyed in favor of an invisible Redeemer-god, rather than celestial spheres. This was the continual work since the time of Moses.

The Norse recorded these various clashes in epic form, and like the Greeks, they found inspiration for warlike hostilities with neighbors who more than likely favored diverse pantheons, as did all cultures around the world (India still retains classic mixed pantheons and regional favoritism). However, the chief religious story was of the birth and passage of power from the Heavenly Father to a Son of Heaven. Eventually, in Hellenistic times, this ancient Egyptian myth/remembering became humanized. It was the result of the Hebrew and Hindu desire to abandon worship of the aforementioned Golden Bull and all celestial spheres (gods and angels) and to follow only the Lord, as mentioned before literalized through the perception of the Sound (Yahweh) that was heard during the Exodus (cross recorded in the Ipuwer papyrus). The literalization of this Lord (into a Christ, Buddha, Laozi, Quetzalcoatl, etc...) meant also the corporealization of these ‘gods’ (aliens, experienced previously in trance form through shamanic pursuits, but later seen as spheres in the sky when the plasma sheath fell (supposedly when sky fell)) into a bodily form.

The Elohim of the pantheon was reduced to a singular El, which was further transferred into a corporeal identity of a messiah in multiple traditions worldwide, following the last “ragnarok” when Mars (Ares/Thor) went “mad” and the “Scar-faced tyrant” came to earth and brought the Taoist proverbial “world of red dust” upon us. It took the form of a Kali-tongue, a sickle of death and destruction which dumped more sands upon the Earth, and destroyed a number of biblical civilizations. The final catastrophic thunderbolts equalized Earth to her younger brother, both born of the same ecliptic as father Saturn, and Mars and Earth (with its “Watcher,” the Moon) were both cast away from Zeus. Apollo “grew” and his twin Aphrodite (the Moon) came to symbolize the new yin and yang.

The main proofs of these changes are not only in physical evidences but in calendrical evidence. To this date we maintain that December is the 10th month, literally, although we have 12 months. The length of the year changed somewhat (but not so much as to violate overmuch angular momentum) from 350 days to 365 days. Many cultures had already maintained a 12 month calendar going back to when 360 days formed a year. A

few, like Rome had reduced to ten months when - again worldwide - cultures had to redefine the calendar. Apparently the sun had changed directions and the Earth had already flipped or tilted; the records are clear but ambiguous. At one point we passed too close to Sol (new Helios), and the planet nearly burned up (several American tribes said that the war of the gods had boiled stone and melted the earth, but afterwards rocks glowed red in the sun). It isn't surprising that at this time the earliest conceptions of a Hell were conceived of, while man was stuck living under ground and it was hot (Hel means "covered").

But, fortunately for humanity, we were quickly established in a good orbit. However, this did take a number of years, and Sumerian records record a gruesome period of drought and famine during which parents even sometimes ate their own children (as Kronos had). It was truly humanity's darkest hour up until the Holocaust.

Being electrically stratified into discrete orbital shells, the inner rocky planets no longer exerted extreme forces upon us, and the tyranny of Zeus' thunderbolts (vajra) was soon to be forgotten by western cultures on an outer level, but not inside (is it any wonder why the West created the atom bomb?); to be remembered only upon deep inspection of the Bible, Sumerian, Zoroastrian, and Greek records. But for those cultures which had not easily survived the Venus/Exodus event, and certainly struggled as hunter-gatherers through the Mars event (circa 700 BCE) then through a dark age and age of seafaring diffusionism, occasionally truncated by impact errata in such places as the British Isles, Bolivia, and Easter Island); these cultures remembered through oral tradition very clearly or nearly so the events that changed Mankind. Despite the poo-poo's of archaeologists and anthro-apologists, they insisted upon these memories, and to this day have been largely ignored.

In the case of Hindus they recorded them in written form in sanskrit and pali. In the case of Mexico they took the Doggerland calendar of the Olmec and created a complex, imaginative hieroglyphic system, that like Egypt, was based upon a cult of death, heaven ascension, rebirth, and the spirit world. Such cultures retained their entheogenic roots. From as far as Africa to the Sami of Siberia, and from tip to tip in Americas, and all the way to New Zealand where the first 'whites' that Maori discovered upon later arrival, the use of entheogens fueled the obsession with this catastrophic history and the cycles of life and death. In India, again, samsaric religions all espoused similar doctrines to Nordic peoples. These and linguistic commonalities support further the common origins of these advanced religious cultures with the Assyrians and Caucasians, themselves quite nomadic, theistic, warlike, and probably descendants of the aforementioned fallen civilization that gathered at Gobekli Tepe following their own brush with catastrophe in the Age of Leo.

Going back to the Pharaohs: their coming upon the Land of the Gods, and not recalling the age, they set about to first restore the glory of the past, and to mimic it. Building one or two pyramid failures, they eventually discovered the secrets of the building, and set about enslaving diverse peoples, especially Hebrews and Ethiopians, to build lavish tombs of death. These tombs were set near to Giza primarily, and were thereafter, even through the Exodus destruction down into the final kingdoms the subject of intense jealousy, rivalry, and pillaging. In short, throughout each era, they retained these practices, right up until the Age of Gods and Heroes ended; throughout every cycle of destruction and rebirth until the Hellenistic Age (of Pisces) began.

Pre-Islamic bedouins of Arabia came to control the destroyed Egyptian ruins (the riches sought, but the knowledge of the 'gods' was abandoned as worthless), and to found Islamic seeds throughout all the Desert Belt, though the ripening for Islam conquest was not to occur until after the crystallization of the corporeal Savior phenomenon was adopted in the Common Era. Since that time, competing versions from Christianity to Buddhism to Islam to even Religious Taoism have vied up until the modern era for predominance. Even in the 20th century the relatively new western modern man (post "Enlightenment") has revitalized this fervor via scientific occult behaviors and modern mysticism, in the form of mathemagics and Inquisitions (via 'peer review'). The facts of this can be seen through the almost zealous restrictions that occur in mainstream

cosmology, astronomy, physics, and biology. To question 'consensus Science' (a postmodern statement of Faith), even with inescapable hard evidence, is to risk financial ruin, and reputational suicide in the modern priesthood ranks.

(5)

In some cases there are even complete conspiratorial arranged mobbing and book burnings (the same energy as at Alexandria, proving the above hypothesis), and even the ignoring of good, and useful science. Sometimes this is a matter of popularity "cliques" (the who knows who phenomena). In other cases, it is outright politically driven policies, which have unfortunately hampered human progress. Take for instance the debunking of Dark Energy and Dark Matter *before* their inceptions. In the former case, Halton Arp discovered Intrinsic Red Shift 30 years previous to the "discovery" of 'accelerated Expansion' Theory modification of Big Bang (itself the hypothesis of a Catholic Bishop, which of course led to religious fanatical dogmatism). In the latter case of Dark Matter, terrella experiments in 1956 proved conclusively that galactic shapes and solar behaviors could be derived from observed plasma phenomena, itself a lab derived theory dating back all the way to classical electromagnetism and the critical junction in 1905 when Einstein stole the ideas of Henri Poincare and confused the world with unsolvable mathematics; which ironically are used to support Big Bang despite a) him denying the Big Bang and b) the two cosmologies being mathematically incompatible universes.

In the meantime, these two things have also been post-genesis officially falsified via the discovery of baryons (quarks) and plasma filaments and hydrogen bubbles on galactic scales exiting the galactic core. However, the continued ignoring of Intrinsic Redshift has created a bubble of awareness whereby astrophysicists seem blissfully unaware - of their ignorance - of the failure of the Dark Universe model (plasma itself already has a 'dark mode' but is decidedly not invisible).

The discovery of exoplanets and the collapse of the standard solar model; both of mechano-gravity based fusion⁷ and of the "Accretion model"⁸ has precipitated the re-evaluation of ancient mythological descriptions of a) Edin or a Zep Tepi/Golden Age, b) our solar system cosmogony, c) the strange bifurcated arrangement of our solar system and its odd declinations, orbits, and irregularities as well as highly stratified compositions (in mass and atmospheres), and d) the origin of our solar system's [electric] comets.

For with the collapse of the standard solar model has come also simultaneously the collapse of the Oort Cloud model, itself a strangely widely adopted hypothesis with little physical evidence previous to comet missions that then debunked it. (One must wonder if there is divine intervention, indeed, for all of these collapses to occur in tandem). It had been hoped that such missions would find the origins of water; however one new upcoming rival stream of thought has already postulated a far more likely and observed formation method for water, calling it "star water". A rival alternate theory postulates that the [expanding] Earth is hollow but perhaps full of proto-water (EZ water) and that it is oozing up through the mantle. NASA support officially has been scant for hollow Earth, but their zero-gravity experiments with angular momentum are fairly convincing of external crustal displacement. A 'growing' Electric-Earth does conform both to the conservation of mass-energy in plasma streams coming from the sun to Earth and to longitudinal waveforms velocities found in earthquake data that refute an iron-nickel core. Given the well known Newtonian solution to zero gravity in the center of the Earth, the idea of high pressure in the core does seem quite unlikely as compared, say to boiling water-core.

⁷ Stars are now found which are definitely smaller than the 'smallest possible limit', nay they are even Jupiter sized

⁸ Multiple Jupiter sized exoplanets (called "hot Jupiters") have been found far too close to too small a star - TRAPPIST-1 - to be accounted for with accretion, as well as our own solar system which has never formed via simulations of this hypothesis

All needs for a gyre mechanism of a super hot core disappear in plasma electrogeology. The core becomes simply a water filled chamber of charged particles, and the Earth then another voltaic source (a transforming, capacitive battery) in a complex solar circuit; itself a mere "circuit device" in a wider galactic circuit which interacts with the entire Lanakea Super Circuit, now known to demonstrate bi-polarized energy distributions.

The recent falsification of the standard vortex formation model (hot vs cold air) has also bolstered electrometeorology, again completely simultaneous to the sudden discoveries of the Birkeland current (marklund convection) counter-rotation mechanism of polar "storms" upon gas giants Jupiter and Saturn both. On Earth, the clearly electrical nature of vortices, such as Supercells and Hurricanes with a clear inducto-capacitor model has also called into question standard models of clouds, precipitation, and even their relationships perhaps with electrogeology. The sheer weight of clouds, hail, the types of formation, the strata, and the lack of plausible mechanisms for vortex formation without charge separation have all aided this rethinking. The emergence of electrometeorology corollary with the discovery of magnetic tunneling from the sun to Earth, along with the photographic evidence of tropospheric lightning has pushed for a rethinking of the causative mechanisms of earthquakes, hurricanes, and larger climatic behaviors such as el nino and la nina.

Meanwhile, likewise the emergence of new archaeological discoveries, such as new nazca/paracas lines, new geo-earthworks in the Amazon, and underwater cities, have totally challenged the mainstream on all fronts, rendering it incapable in the Age of Information of beating back all the challenges simultaneously. More laboratory evidence and, in some cases, mainstream failures through attempts to prove mainstream ideas (such as using copper to chisel granite or limestone; or finding Dark Matter) have forced alternate theories into common consciousness or at least widespread consciousness. At first it was questioned via inquisitive books and shows, mostly about 'ancient aliens' (again here hypothesized to be an admixture of the shamanistic phenomena and of mythic Star Wars aka the Clash of Titans). But now quite common inquiry in every field from electric arc machining to stonemasonry to hydrology is causing a widespread desire to re-examine known interpreted data. In some cases, such as in Bosnia in investigating the origins of concrete, it is primarily through geology and excavations. In other places it is through theoretical simulations (such as the partially correct Michigan comet impact theory). In some cases it is inclusive of native testimony, albeit the mainstream has not cozied up to the facts of the Sumerian records, Gobekli Tepe, and the discovery of lost cities such as Dwarka. It has in the latter case, and at Gunung Padang actively sought to block further archaeological exploration by claiming a priori knowledge of the facts; a hypothesis which, historically never stands the test of time. This includes also the Bimini Row where good solid underwater exploration threatened to reveal the actual location of Atlantis or an Atlantean culture and so was halted through official channels, as was excavations at Gunung Padang and Dwarka.

The simultaneous rebellion against inquest has led to an untenable position by famed Egyptologist Zahi Hawass that a recently proven discovered chamber (a large one) inside the Great Pyramid was "not important" because he "never found anything with radar." Such a position will receive ridicule in the coming decades and centuries.

The continual denial to observe the engineering and manufacturing facts of the Great Pyramid has frustrated alternative scientists, and even mainstream Egyptologists, who as a new generation are exposed ever more to alternate (ie: non-Victorian) ways of thinking and has fueled the feverish behavior of alien-hypothesizers (Sitchinities), conspiracy theorists (sometimes combined with the former), and fringe behaviorists, such as "Flat Earthers" and mystics. The strong desire of many to return to a Zep Tepi remains, long after the "Fall" and perhaps because of it and despite the insistence of the mainstream to drag us into further bad science. This difference is creating a confusing, but intriguing plethora of research which becomes increasingly difficult to analyze, yet all the more important for the truth to be made out from it.

(6)

As the world nears self-created ragnarok, it beggars the question: can we re-establish the right Science, the life science of the First Age of mankind's awakening, and use our benefit of hydrocarbon showering from the Exodus event (Venus' tail) to actually move ourselves into a true age of unlimited energy, as Tesla foretold was possible? Or is our subconsciousness to remain stuck on end of the world scenarios, for which we endlessly reverberate in media and social fear, and yet have done nothing to prevent and perhaps only hastened?

So far, despite our worldwide catharsis with the release of Star Wars and on screen destruction of the plasma ejecting "Death Star," (clearly the Morning/Evening Star of Venus) we have as of yet been unable to enjoy the fruits of our scientific revolution, except perhaps via our technocracy. Yet happiness for some alone has been misery to nearly all and which, of course has within it the seeds of widespread pollution and destruction as well as usefulness (but decreasing with each loss of nutrition, bee hive, and planned obsolescence for the sake of profit). We have gone from dressing in hand-woven riches and wearing gemstones to being clothed in cheap rags and wearing plastic; and even consuming it!

Our crazed obsession with value and economics; its admixture with war, hearkens directly back to the Age of Heroes, of plunder and Sea Peoples and up through Vikings and piracy. A mentality of poverty, in a universe swimming with charges and energy for us to tap into, if we would listen to the Tesla's and Leedskalnins of the world. Perhaps we are, at this point, thoroughly impressed and convinced that to get energy means to combust or destroy; and yet it is demonstrable through direct observation and astronomical evidence that we can transfer and transform energy, in some cases to great efficiency and over long distances. We have placed upon ourselves limits, and yet quantum electrodynamics laughs at these limits and plasma physics challenges us to seek to connect to a wider circuit. We are receivers of a true Ethereal mechanics, by means of which we can tap into the very energy of void-space and make use of the efficiency of Birkeland currents. What will we do with this newfound enlightenment?

Indeed, this echoes our greatest spiritual faiths, which at their root contain energetics (meditation and supplementation and working with the nerves and brain through diverse methods) that prove the efficacy of health and longevity cultivation. Yet: we poison our food, air, water, and now minds like battered, abused addicts. At some point we may pass an unreturnable position, if we do not act quickly to admit our faults, and the facts, and to correct to the way Nature is, if not also the whole Truth of our collective human history and the Hell we have been through *together*.

Therefore it is imperative that this new cosmological awareness take root and be understood. The various ragnarok cycles - and their instigators - we have survived. And with the taming of the moon, of Venus, and Mars there is no particular evidence, other than the degrading magnetosphere, that we will undergo such diluvian or super-hurricane force wind destructions again. Whilst in our Enlightenment of the Age of Heroes we discovered the benefit of discipline and made it a rigor and a nightmare of waste of life and energy, we now know that no particular clock rests upon us, save whatever individual faith dictates (again in reference to the Son of Heaven/Savior phenomenon which cannot be proven or disproven and may be impossible to extricate ourselves from even if unfounded.)

We have all the energy we need around us, and the time and space to do it. While it is true the seasons are slightly more negative for us than they were in the Purple Dawn of mankind, they are more stable than they were in the Age of Gods and Heroes. Furthermore, the species-ending thunderbolts of the gods do not rain

down upon us any longer, and our terrestrial lightnings are beneficial, if not frightening a bit (for their reminder of the “Divine Power”). It is slightly possible for the moon to do so, but each year it gets further away from us and so the permittivity increases our protection. We have learned both of the sword and of the pen. We have learned of our energetic bodies, and of the various chemistries governing life and material mastery. Wizardry is now so commonplace it is come to be ordinary and is actually reversing, to where people seek the supernatural or superstitious, mostly for such entertainment and wisdom sources. Characters like Yoda or Gandalf represent to us the teaching invisible hand that uses that Unified Force (Tao) that we have already discovered, if not the bottom of its marvels at least its form and name: electromagnetism. Just recently it was even discovered that we can achieve far higher efficiency of energy transfer through the Birkeland Currents, which degrade by a mere $1/\sqrt{r}$, which at a distance of 50x is 700+% more efficient than a wire, and many times more efficient than a magnetic or electric field.

Tesla, a century ago, predicted our ability and likelihood to reach a place where we can transfer energy wirelessly through the Earth.

I take a further three steps:

1. We will be able to far surpass the Atlanteans in harnessing Earthen vibrations to generate electricity.
2. We will be able to tap into the solar wind and the capacitance of the Earth, on various levels; even through waystations located in deeply laid robotic run mines; and to transform this into everything from space station power to plasma thunderbolts to protect us from asteroids; to terraforming stations on Mars. We will even be able to transform mere light and radio wave into transferable electricity, as well as master the mysterious powers of sound.
3. We will be able to transmute various kinds of “elements” through an improved Chemistry model, which is itself based upon a more correct understanding of electro-gravity and light (which is not a particle at all, though it may be modeled as one for ease). We will be able to provide these powers in homes for cleansing water, air, and body; and it will fascinate our society and become a religion-less devotion; however we choose to deal with our need for Salvation.

The mastering of sound and electricity has already begun. It started with Tesla and Leedskalnin, and has continued up until the modern day of resonance experiments. It, the Expanding Earth, and the wireless power transfer are inexplicably related, and this technology remains a long dead secret of the Atlanteans, or whoever built the religious stations in South Africa as well as Egypt and Yucatan. Whatever their secret, it does seem likely that we will reverse engineer the magnificent Great Pyramid completely within this century and seek to build our own, highly technocratic models; and then to reduce their sizes, and combine them perhaps, with our growing computerized “internet of things.” Imagine a “great pyramid” generator/resonator that fits inside your home and receives wireless power (via Tesla coils and scalar magnetic waves) from the Earth-transformer itself; and which also functions as a computer and home management device!

This may, in time meet with a biological engineering effort to derive energy and computing power from life itself; but it remains to be seen how our technocracy and our war-besotted paradigm of Science will intermingle with Nature, the original laboratory. For now it appears we prefer to do much of it by “reinventing the wheel.” Such as it is, it is much preferable to an unnecessary Ragnarok by [Nuclear] Fire!⁹

Conclusion

A new cosmogony and cosmology is emerging which, like pearls on a string, ties together the diverse hypotheses and testimony worldwide, and provides new, and improved models for scientific inquiry.

⁹ “Investments in Ragnarok,” Sf. R. Careaga, 2018

Furthermore this may alleviate humanity of the burden of guilt for things which we now know we certainly had no power to control, being altogether powerless to stop such celestial events, and existing as mere ants upon a floodplain. If we can overcome our fears and addictions, our self-abnegation, and come to embrace our natural scientific and spiritual gifts, and learn to follow the wisdoms unlocked during such trials as mankind has experienced without the perversities of self-destructive obsessions, we may in fact be on the cusp of greater discoveries and higher mental evolution.

Otherwise, we may simply be wasting a golden opportunity and a rareness of time and season, so to speak, to reverse engineer the past to better construct our future; and provide a safer world based upon new natural, peaceful paradigms that benefit all, and safeguard children especially. To help heal ourselves and our collective unconscious abuses, is perhaps the greatest challenge, and most improbable. Yet it is, after all, the ultimate pursuit of the wise and compassionate from the beginning of the Age of Heroes and perhaps extending well into the Age of Gods.

Just as the wise and just Sumerian kings on occasion boycotted the gods to correct their behavior, perhaps we too can recognize the failures of our new gods: technology, authority, economy, entertainment, and politics, and censure them into obedience to higher principles of virtue and compassion, in order that we may discipline ourselves into reaching the greater dreams we so clearly never give up upon, be they star travel or ease of existence or even simply clothing, feeding, and providing clean water to every man, woman, and child on this small rock existing precariously and mostly unprotected now in a vast sea of plasma-electric energy; moving from one age to another, and out from behind the dark cloud of gas into full view of our galactic core, which will indeed bathe us in new, profound, powerful radiation whether or not we are ready. Perhaps it is revelation; or perhaps satori (enlightenment). Either way, the choice is ultimately ours, and not the gods.

EPEMC Papers by the Author

Sorted by chronology of authorship, rather than publication.

1. Plasma Petroglyphs, Geoglyphs, and the Megafauna Extinction; Re-examining key Allegewi-Hopewellian Mounds and Serpent Effigies, comparisons with Peratt plasmoid shapes produced in laboratories to determine viability for reclassification of glyph genesis and proposal of a radically alternative vector of megafauna extinction.
2. Extended-plasma-electromagnetic Cosmology (EPEMC whitepaper)¹⁰
3. On the Origins of Religions¹¹
4. Investments in Ragnarok; Comparisons and Conclusions from the study of Media, Business, and Government investments in End of the World myth, story, and preparation.
5. Unboxing Atlantis; A top-down review of what we know, and don't know, about the Atlantean through Megalithic Period continents and cities; 36,000 - 2,000 YBP¹²
6. Analysis of Signs in Greco-Roman-Nordic Culture and Modern Use; Using EPEMC to decipher hidden origins of signs & glyphs related to the zodiacs and days
7. Our Plasma-Electromagnetic Sky; Application of Hollow-Expanding-Growing-Electromagnetic Earth Hypothesis with particular respect to the Earth's Atmosphere starting from the Lithosphere and ascending Altitude.¹³
8. Our Magnetic Universe; A Top-Down Review of Phases of Magnetic Theory Development, with accompanying histogram and comparison with Aether/Unified Field Theory¹⁴
9. Ferris Wheels and the Dionysian Irony; The subconscious drive of thrill, abandonment of caution, and the iconography of Amusement/Thrill Parks

¹⁰ First introduction to Electrothermal Vine Hypothesis

¹¹ First cache of HEGEME/PEMS evidence to formulate EPEMC; massive chart of comparison of religious symbols in Appendix; table of period eras and massive table of gods vs planets

¹² Introduction to HEGEME hypothesis; Megalith chart and size comparison graph; table of sudden upthrust and downthrust values from 12kya; first mention of membranaric crust

¹³ PEMS and expansion on HEGEME; expansion on membranaric crust; Appendices include Glossary and Laws of Physics; introduction of Laws of Energy and Laws of Life; tables of equations; Introduction of Spheres of Heaven and Earth hypothesis; introduction of why Life occurs

¹⁴ AF/UAF vs. PEM/EPEMC; historiographies of key components of PEMC; Appendices include Glossary and Laws of Physics; introduction of Laws of Energy and Laws of Life; tables of equations